

Simulation Model for Page Replacement Algorithm

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Abstract—*This paper aims to simulate and imitate the work of page replacement algorithms in operating systems. In an operating system that uses paging to manage memory, a page replacement algorithm is needed to select the page that needs to be replaced when a new page appears. Page replacement becomes necessary when a page fault occurs and there are no free page frames in memory. By knowing the work of page replacement algorithms, it can enhance the performance of the operating system and make our computers more efficient and faster. The purpose of this research is to enhance theoretical knowledge of the page replacement algorithms through simulation, and improve practical ability, how the algorithms work and compare different algorithms of page replacement algorithms. Through simulation models, it allows us to understand and master the basic theory and functions of the operating system through programming and simulation experiments.*

Keywords—*Simulation, Model, Operating Systems, memory management, Page Replacement Algorithm, Page Fault, Victim Frame, First-In-First-Out (FIFO), Most Frequently Used (MFU), The Least Recently Used (LRU) and The Optimal algorithm.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Computer simulation has different meanings, including Frigg and Reiss broad meaning, which refers to the entire process of constructing, using, and justifying a model that involves analytically intractable mathematics.^[1] Simulation is the imitation of some real thing, process or system. The act of simulating something in general represents certain key characteristics or behaviors of a selected physical or abstract system.^[2] Memory management is one of the elementary functions of any operating system and does not have multiple programming without designing effective algorithms that manage memory.^[3] As well as for virtual memory management necessity use effective page replacement algorithms to decide which page should be omitted from memory if page fault occurs.^[4] Pages replacement is an essential concept in memory management system. When the operating system creates the process with system calls^[5], pages is must to be in the main memory. The purpose of page replacement algorithms is to reduce the number of replacements^[6]. The model allows us to achieve the solution of the analyzed problem by performing simulations until satisfactory results are achieved^[7].

II. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

Pages replacement algorithms in operating systems are very important for more efficient memory management and a lot of research has appeared in recent years that has addressed this topic.

In April 2011, the IACSIT International Journal of Engineering and Technology published a research paper by Amit S. Chavan et al. titled "Comparison of Page Replacement Algorithms." The study primarily focused primarily on formulating new page replacement approaches that adapt to changing workloads. and compared traditional page replacement algorithms such as LRU and CLOCK with modern approaches such as LIRS, CLOCK-Pro, ARC, and CAR. ^[4]

In December 2017, IEEE published a paper by Kartik Moudgil et al., This paper proposes an algorithm to perform this page replacement task and objectively summarizes, evaluates and represents classical and modern page replacement algorithms, with a qualitative analysis of their performance in specific scenarios. ^[8]

In May 2018, Sourabh Shastri et al. conducted a study analyzing three-page replacement algorithms: First-In-First-Out (FIFO), Least Recently Used (LRU), and Optimal Page Replacement (OPT), using C# in Visual Studio .NET. ^[9]

In October 2020, Tri Dharma Putra et al. conducted an analysis of the random page replacement algorithm in operating systems. Their study examines three case studies exploring the behavior and performance of this algorithm. ^[10]

In October 2021, Researchers Minseon Cho and Donghyun Kang introduced, that embeds single-layer perceptron neural network algorithms to enable an intelligent eviction policy. In addition, ML-CLOCK employs preference rules that consider the features of the underlying storage media (e.g., asymmetric read and write costs and efficient write patterns). ^[11]

This paper introduces a Java-based simulation model designed to replicate the behavior of page replacement algorithms. The model generates a random reference sequence of pages, applies various algorithms—such as FIFO, LRU, Optimal, and MFU—and computes the number of page faults for each method. By adjusting the number of frames, the simulation enhances comprehension of these algorithms, making it a valuable educational tool for undergraduate students and those interested in page replacement techniques. It facilitates a deeper understanding, promotes knowledge dissemination, and helps identify the most efficient algorithm.

III. PURPOSE OF PAGE REPLACEMENT ALGORITHMS

Page replacement algorithms are essential mechanisms in operating systems that optimize memory management when virtual memory reaches full capacity. When a new page must be loaded into physical memory, but no free space is available, these algorithms decide which existing page should be replaced. Over the years, various algorithms have been developed, each of them aims to minimize the number of page faults and improve system performance.^[12] Page replacement algorithms propose different ways to determine which page to replace and the goal for all algorithms is to reduce the number of page faults.

IV. GENERAL IDEA OF THE PAGE REPLACEMENT ALGORITHM

In this section, we will describe how Page Replacement Algorithms works

1. Generate random reference string
2. Find the location of the desired page on the hard disk
3. Look for a free frame in the main memory:
 - a. If the free frame exists, use it
 - b. Else, use the Page Replacement algorithm to determine a victim frame
4. Swap desired page into a victim frame that (newly) free frame.
5. Update the page and frame tables
6. Resume the process
7. Calculate no of Page Fault and print Simulation output

Figure 1: Flowchart of Simulation Model for Page Replacement Algorithms

V. THE FIRST-IN-FIRST-OUT ALGORITHM (FIFO)

The FIFO algorithm is one of the simplest pages replacement algorithms and its idea is to replace the oldest page in the main memory ^[9]. The FIFO page replacement algorithm is easy to implement but it suffers from Belady’s anomaly ^[13], which means some reference strings produce unexpected results called Belady’s anomaly i.e. by increasing the number of page frames, the page fault also increases. Figure (5) a, b illustrates the phenomenon of Belady’s anomaly. As the number of frames increases from three to four, the number of page faults for some random sequences increases. Table (1) illustrates how FIFO algorithm using three frames works with the following reference string 7 0 1 2 0 3 0 4 2 3 3 2 1 2 0 1 7 0 1.

Table (1) The First-in-First-out Page Replacement Algorithm

reference string																			
7	0	1	2	0	3	0	4	2	3	0	3	2	1	2	0	1	7	0	1
		1	1	1	1	0	0	0	3	3	3	3	3	2	2	2	2	2	1
	0	0	0	0	3	3	3	2	2	2	2	2	1	1	1	1	1	0	0
7	7	7	2	2	2	2	4	4	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	7	7	7
m	m	m	m	h	m	m	m	m	m	m	h	h	m	m	h	h	m	m	m

15 page faults, where (m represents a miss and h represents a hit).

VI. OPTIMAL PAGE REPLACEMENT

Optimal Algorithm has good performance and often gave minimum number of page fault but is difficult to implement in real operating systems. [15] In this algorithm, pages are replaced which are not used for the longest time in the future, as illustrated in the Table (2), the same reference string is used algorithm as follows: 7 0 1 2 0 3 0 4 2 3 3 2 1 2 0 1 7 0 1 and the same page frame with size = 3 is chosen. Table 2 shows how the optimal algorithm chooses the victim frame.

Table (2) Optimal Page Replacement Algorithm

reference string																			
7	0	1	2	0	3	0	4	2	3	0	3	2	1	2	0	1	7	0	1
		1	1	1	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	1	1	1	1	7	7	7
	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	4	4	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	1	1
7	7	7	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	0	0	0
m	m	m	m	h	m	h	m	h	h	m	H	h	m	h	h	h	m	h	h

9-page faults

VII. LEAST RECENTLY USED ALGORITHM (LRU)

LRU algorithm considers the recently used page has higher chance to use more than the other pages. This algorithm is more efficient than FIFO because it has information about the pages used before [14]. Table (3) shows how the LRU algorithm selects victim frame with same previous sequence of pages and same frame size

Table (3) LRU Page Replacement Algorithm

reference string																			
7	0	1	2	0	3	0	4	2	3	0	3	2	1	2	0	1	7	0	1
		1	1	1	3	3	3	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	7	7	7
	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	3	3	3	3	3	3	0	0	0	0	0
7	7	7	2	2	2	2	4	4	4	0	0	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
M	m	m	m	h	M	h	m	m	m	m	h	h	m	h	m	h	m	h	h

12-page faults

VIII. MOST RECENTLY USED (MRU)

In this algorithm, the page will be replaced which has been used recently. Belady’s anomaly can occur in this algorithm, as in the FIFO algorithm. If we consider the previous page reference string 7 0 1 2 0 3 0 4 2 3 0 3 2 1 2 0 1 7 0 1 with 3 frames, Table 4 shows the number of page faults using the MRU page replacement algorithm.

Table (4) MRU Page Replacement Algorithm

reference string																			
7	0	1	2	0	3	0	4	2	3	0	3	2	1	2	0	1	7	0	1
		1	2	2	2	2	2	2	3	0	3	2	1	2	0	1	1	1	1
	0	0	0	0	3	0	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	7	0	0
m	m	m	m	h	m	m	m	h	m	m	m	m	m	m	m	m	h	m	h

16-page faults

IX. SIMULATION MODEL TO COMPARE BETWEEN FIFO, OPTIMAL, LRU AND MRU ALGORITHMS

This section presents the simulation model and highlights the results of various page replacement algorithms. A comparison is conducted among FIFO, LRU, OPTIMAL, and MRU to determine which algorithm generates the fewest page faults. The simulation was run multiple times with different reference strings, and the results displayed the number of page faults in each iteration, as illustrated in Table (5) and Table (6).

Figure (3) shows the simulation results for different algorithms using 10 random reference sequences with three frames, while Figure (4) shows a simulation model showing the number of page faults for different page replacement algorithms, which were tested using 10 random reference sequences with both three and four frames. Figures (5a and 5b) show the simulation results for the FIFO algorithm, applying 10 random reference sequences with three and four frames. Figure (6) shows a simulation model analyzing the page faults for the LRU algorithm, using 10 random reference sequences with three and four frames, Figure (7) shows the Output of simulation program in Java for FIFO algorithm whereas Figure (8) shows the Output of simulation program in Java for LRU algorithm.

Table (5) Results of the Simulation Model Comparing Different Page Replacement Algorithms

Ser	Reference String	Algorithm	No of Frame = 4		No of Frame = 3	
			Hit	Mis	Hit	Mis
1-	7 0 1 2 0 3 0 4 2 3 0 3 2 1 2 0 1 7 0 1	FIFO	10	10	5	15
		LRU	12	8	8	12
		Optimal	12	8	11	9
		MRU	8	12	4	16
2-	1 0 1 2 0 3 0 4 2 3 0 3 2 1 2 0 1 2 0 1	FIFO	12	8	12	8
		LRU	14	6	10	10
		Optimal	14	6	13	7
		MRU	10	10	7	13
3-	1 0 4 2 0 3 0 4 2 3 0 3 2 1 2 3 1 2 4 1	FIFO	14	6	5	15
		LRU	13	7	9	11
		Optimal	14	6	12	8
		MRU	9	11	6	14
4-	2 0 4 2 0 3 0 4 2 3 0 3 2 1 2 3 1 2 4 1	FIFO	14	6	9	11
		LRU	14	6	10	10
		Optimal	15	5	13	7
		MRU	13	7	7	13
5-	2 0 4 2 0 3 5 4 2 3 5 3 2 1 2 3 1 2 4 1	FIFO	12	8	11	9
		LRU	11	9	9	11
		Optimal	14	6	12	8
		MRU	7	13	7	13
6-	2 6 4 2 1 3 5 4 2 3 6 3 2 1 2 3 1 2 4 1	FIFO	9	11	5	15
		LRU	9	11	8	12
		Optimal	12	8	10	10
		MRU	6	14	4	16
7-	2 3 4 2 1 3 5 4 2 3 3 3 2 1 2 3 1 2 4 1	FIFO	11	9	11	9
		LRU	12	8	9	11
		Optimal	14	6	12	8
		MRU	10	10	8	12
8-	2 3 3 2 1 3 5 4 2 3 3 3 2 1 2 3 1 2 5 1	FIFO	9	11	11	9
		LRU	12	8	11	9
		Optimal	14	6	13	7
		MRU	14	6	9	11
9-	7 3 3 2 1 3 5 4 2 3 3 3 2 1 2 3 1 2 5 1	FIFO	10	10	10	10
		LRU	11	9	10	10
		Optimal	13	7	12	8
		MRU	8	12	7	13
10-	7 3 3 2 1 3 3 4 2 3 3 3 2 1 2 3 1 2 4 1	FIFO	15	5	11	9
		LRU	15	5	12	8
		Optimal	15	5	13	7
		MRU	10	10	8	12

Table (6): Simulation Model Outputs for the Number of Page Faults Comparing Different Page Replacement Algorithms

FIFO with 4 Frame	LRU with 4 Frame	Optimal with 4 Frame	MRU with 4 Frame	FIFO with 3 Frame	LRU with 3 Frame	Optimal with 3 Frame	MRU with 3 Frame
10	8	8	12	15	12	9	16
8	6	6	10	8	10	7	13
6	7	6	11	15	11	8	14
6	6	5	7	11	10	7	13
8	9	6	13	9	11	8	13
11	11	8	14	15	12	10	16
9	8	6	10	9	11	8	12
11	8	6	6	9	9	7	11
10	9	7	12	10	10	8	13
5	5	5	10	9	8	7	12

Figure (2): Simulation results for different algorithms with 10 random reference sequences with 4 frames

Figure (3): Simulation results for different algorithms with 10 random reference sequences with 3 frames

Figure (4): Simulation model for No of Page fault for different page replacement algorithms with 10 random reference sequences with 3 frames and 4 frames

Figure (5a) Simulation results of the FIFO algorithm for 10 random reference sequences with 3 frames and 4 frames

Figure (5b) Simulation results of the FIFO algorithm for 10 random reference sequences with 3 frames and 4 frames

Figure (6) Page fault simulation model for LRU algorithm with 10 random reference sequences with 3 frames and 4 frames

And in more detail When we run a simulation model to show mechanism work of FIFO algorithm, with Random References string 7, 0, 1, 2, 0, 3, 0, 4, 2, 3, 0, 3, 2, 1, 2, 0, 1, 7, 0, 1 we obtain the following output.

Page fault simulation model for LRU algorithm with 10 random reference sequences with 3 frames and 4 frames

Incoming	Frame 1	Frame 2	Frame 3	Frame 4
7	7	-	-	-
0	7	0	-	-
1	7	0	1	-
2	7	0	1	2
0	7	0	1	2
3	3	0	1	2
0	3	0	1	2
4	3	4	1	2
2	3	4	1	2
3	3	4	1	2
0	3	4	0	2
3	3	4	0	2
2	3	4	0	2
1	3	4	0	1
2	2	4	0	1
0	2	4	0	1
1	2	4	0	1
7	2	7	0	1
0	2	7	0	1
1	2	7	0	1
Total Page Faults:	10			

Figure (7) Output of simulation program in Java for FIFO algorithm.

Similarly, When we run a simulation model to understand the mechanism of LRU algorithm with previous References string 7, 0, 1, 2, 0, 3, 0, 4, 2, 3, 0, 3, 2, 1, 2, 0, 1, 7, 0, 1 we obtain the following output.

Incoming	Frame 1	Frame 2	Frame 3	Frame 4
7				
0	7	-	-	-
1	7	0	-	-
2	7	0	1	-
0	7	0	1	2
3	7	0	1	2
0	3	0	1	2
4	3	0	1	2
2	3	4	1	2
3	3	4	1	2
0	3	4	1	2
3	3	4	0	2
2	3	4	0	2
1	3	4	0	2
2	3	4	0	1
0	2	4	0	1
1	2	4	0	1
7	2	4	0	1
0	2	7	0	1
1	2	7	0	1
.	2	7	0	1
Total Page Faults:	10			

Figure (8) Output of simulation program in Java for LRU algorithm.

X. RESULTS

When comparing the algorithms (FIFO, LRU, Optimal, and MRU) with the same number of pages, the same sequence, and the same number of frames, the simulation results showed different results with the same sequence and the same number of frames. As noted, the optimal algorithm and the LRU algorithm gave the least number of page faults. but Optimal algorithm suffers of difficult to implement because it requires future knowledge of reference strings. By repeating the simulation model a large number of times, we can increase our understanding of the mechanism of work of page replacement algorithms compared to other algorithms. The algorithm that gives the least number of page faults is the most suitable and best algorithm among the other algorithms.

XI. CONCLUSION

The purpose of this paper is to simulate page replacement algorithms to understand how these algorithms work and to achieve the best system performance in page replacement using the algorithm that gives the least number of page faults. In short, page replacement algorithms are essential for efficient management of computer memory. They help ensure that the system runs smoothly by reducing the number of times it needs to fetch data from slower storage to faster storage. Different algorithms, such as FIFO and LRU, have their pros and cons, and choosing the right algorithm depends on the specific needs of the system and the applicability of those algorithms in the operating system. Understanding these algorithms can help improve system performance and make our computers faster and more efficient.

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